

Status Report

Use Case Projects

05.09.2023

NFDI 4
BIODIVERSITY
BIODIVERSITY, ECOLOGY & ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

Strengthening the network of biodiversity data and service providers in Germany: User engagement in NFDI4Biodiversity

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Published by

German Federation for Biological Data (GFBio e.V.), Mary-Somerville-Str. 2-4, 28359 Bremen, Germany

Acknowledgements

The authors of this article have drawn on various preliminary work from the GFBio and NFDI4Biodiversity networks in preparing this report, and references have been provided wherever possible. Thanks to all those who are not named. A special thanks go to Merle Schwarten, Maria Meister, and Lars Möller, who revised and edited the text.

The work was supported by the German Research Foundation DFG under the grant agreement number [442032008](#) (NFDI4Biodiversity). NFDI4Biodiversity is part of NFDI, the National Research Data Infrastructure in Germany (www.nfdi.de).

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Executive Summary

The availability of biodiversity data is key to making informed decisions about the sustainable use and conservation of biodiversity. NFDI4Biodiversity is one of 16 National Research Data Infrastructures (NFDI) in Germany that develops the basis for the availability and exchange of biodiversity data, tools and services between different stakeholders in science, political decision making and society. With 50 partner institutions, NFDI4Biodiversity covers many facets of biodiversity but the functionality of the decentralised data infrastructure is based on a thorough understanding of the needs of its partners.

To reach and connect the German biodiversity data and infrastructure community and create mutual benefit, use cases have been developed to support specific or exemplary data-related issues with the tools and services provided by NFDI4Biodiversity. We present experiences from a 2.5 year phase of user engagement in NFDI4Biodiversity, where we actively involved key actors and documented successes, stumbling blocks, and lessons learned. Consistent with the FAIR principles, 26 use cases promote data mobilisation, interoperability, and data integration from multiple sources and include both technical and regulatory support and training. The needs of different stakeholders for effective data sharing, including legal and technical aspects, biodiversity data collection, annotation and synchronization, analysis and visualisation vary widely, making networking activities challenging. However, the complexity and fragmentation of the biodiversity data, data infrastructures, tools, and service landscape will not add value without concerted action to integrate existing activities.

Introduction

Setting the Scene

Biodiversity data are essential to understand how human activities and climate change affect biodiversity change around the world. Numerous countries acknowledge the importance of accessible biodiversity data in making informed choices about sustainability and conservation. They seek to promote stakeholder networks, develop informatics methods, and customize them for diverse organizations and federated biodiversity data systems. The objective is to enable continuous data mobilization, updates, and the sharing of expertise to improve preservation efforts. Biodiversity data infrastructures are realised in both community-specific international networks (e.g., <https://biodiversityknowledgehub.eu/>; <https://gbif.org> and others), as well as national biodiversity data infrastructures (e.g., Schulman et al. 2021, Rosa et al. 2021; Pacifici 2018, and others). These provide the foundation for data availability and data sharing at multiple scales among various stakeholders from science, political decision making and society, including researchers, professionals and government agencies as well as interested laypersons, citizen scientists, and civil society organisations. In Germany, for example, a multitude of biodiversity data infrastructures are maintained by research organisations, expert organisations, natural history collections, and governmental agencies. Some are broad in scope,

others are highly specialised, representing only a niche with a narrow slice of the multidimensional space of biodiversity data (Bingham 2017). Many data infrastructures were built for specific organisational contexts, with little or no consolidation at the organisational level (Hardisty et al. 2020; Star and Griesemer 1989). Some biodiversity data infrastructures are internationally connected and provide a wide range of services that could be of interest to others. Others are limited in staff, cost or time, so there is no capacity or knowledge to extend or implement additional or latest tools, techniques, and data standards. And for many existing data infrastructures, long-term availability is not guaranteed.

Data spans different scales, time periods, and levels of quality assurance, and are collected for a variety of reasons, from governmental mandates, such as monitoring and reporting, to natural history interests, and scientific research. In recent years, sophisticated technological innovations have emerged to assist in the generation, assessment and processing of biodiversity data for monitoring and documentation processes (Kosmala et al. 2016; McKinley et al. 2017; Pocock et al. 2017; Thornhill et al. 2021, Boyd et al. 2021, Bird et al. 2014; Geldmann et al. 2016). In addition, the ongoing digitization of historical (and recent) data is also helping to improve the biodiversity data landscape. All of this ultimately helps to expand biodiversity knowledge and open new perspectives for research and actionable discoveries. While a wealth of biodiversity data now exists, there is a lack of coordinated infrastructure (Walters and Scholes 2017) or collaborative organisational structures for biodiversity data through the sharing of data, resources, and expertise among stakeholders. As a result, there is still no way to ensure that these data effectively inform decision making and practical implementation at the national level (Walters and Scholes 2017; Kühl et al. 2020).

The German National Research Data Infrastructure NFDI

In response to large amounts of publicly funded data lost in the past and the predicted exponential data growth in the future, the German Science Minister Conference launched a joint initiative of the 16 German states and the federal government to fund a National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, “Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur”; <https://www.nfdi.de>). Within the NFDI, research communities and IT infrastructure providers team up in several consortia spanning different scientific disciplines to provide tailored data services within a specific domain. Domains can be defined by data types, research methodology or discipline (RfII 2016 - Performance through diversity). Initial funding is provided for five years. All consortia are expected to implement the FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al., 2016). The 26 consortia funded to-date cooperate within the NFDI association to enable systematic access and linking of valuable resources across all disciplines and make them (re-)usable in the long term. The consortia were selected in a moderated, peer-reviewed process in order to cover research and societal needs in Germany as broadly as possible.

The NFDI4Biodiversity consortium

NFDI4Biodiversity (<https://www.nfdi4biodiversity.org>) was established as one of the first NFDI consortia and consists of about 50 partner institutions - ranging from research organisations, universities, scientific IT centres and natural history collections to government agencies, expert organisations, and citizen science initiatives. NFDI4Biodiversity is one of the largest NFDI consortia. Data resources cover the multitude of facets of biodiversity from genes to species, functions, interactions and ecosystems, as well as the related environmental data. The partners pool their scientific and technical expertise to provide a broad service portfolio for handling biodiversity and environmental data and to develop it further in close cooperation with users from research and practice previously disconnected infrastructure projects and harmonise their workflows. To this end, the consortium partners offer added value to the biodiversity community, particularly by providing access to advanced technologies and a comprehensive stock of biodiversity and environmental data, methods and tools for archiving, publishing, searching and analysing data that are suitable for everyday use and proven in practice and by connecting people through an expert forum for the safe and competent handling of data for broad and responsible use. A cooperation agreement governs the responsibilities between the partners. NFDI4Biodiversity creates the technical conditions and the infrastructure for the community to work with data collaboratively and across institutional boundaries on a provided service platform. The cooperation of the partner network is guided by the needs of users and stakeholders in science, politics, nature conservation and landscape management for reliable data, e.g. for the development of improved knowledge based measures for the conservation of biodiversity. In this way, the network increases the mobilisation of data for research and resource-management, and enriches the contribution of disparate monitoring efforts. The consortium partners form a strong network that can operate the services in a collaborative and sustainable way and preserve resources for the long term. All partners agreed to make existing data discoverable and reusable in accordance with the FAIR principles and hereby contribute to good scientific practice. NFDI4Biodiversity also promotes the adoption of data standards already agreed by the community, such as ABCD, DarwinCore, MixS, EML and others (<https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2012.740085>). These types of data annotations and metadata descriptions improve the visibility and transparency of data, making it easier to select for networking activities, linking to additional applications and specific activities. Teaching and training materials are provided to facilitate daily work, answer biodiversity questions, and inspire new projects. The partner network addresses five task areas (1) promoting community engagement (2involve), (2) being concerned with national and international networking (2connect), (3) aiming for biodiversity data preservation and certification (2consolidate), by establishing a Research Data Commons (RDC, 4all & 4future), and (5) a coordination and governance structure. This report presents the results of the community engagement task area (2involve) after 2.5 years.

Scope

Despite a broad willingness and awareness for sharing and adding value through data in the German biodiversity community, the needs of different stakeholders for

effective data sharing, including legal and technical aspects, biodiversity data collection, annotation and synchronisation, analysis and visualisation vary widely, making networking activities challenging. We present experiences from a 2.5 year phase of user engagement in NFDI4Biodiversity, where we actively involved key stakeholders and documented successes, pitfalls and lessons learned. We focus on the following aspects:

1. Use case selection
2. Onboarding
3. Project Planning
4. Needs assessment and development of work structures and task similarities in different use cases for mutual benefits
5. First results
6. Lessons learned

Results and discussion

Use Case Selection & Process

In order to involve the German biodiversity data and infrastructure community we decided to establish use cases to reach and connect the target communities and support them on their way to making their data FAIR. The basic idea for establishing use cases was to provide support for specific or exemplary data related issues with tools and services provided by NFDI4Biodiversity. In accordance with the FAIR principles, use cases foster data mobilisation, interoperability, and integration from multiple sources, and include both technical and legal support and training. The strategy for achieving these goals was to (1) to select as many use cases as possible representing the different groups of data holders, (2) identify their needs, (3) support them in solving their issues and (4) make their data available. Use cases are set up with partners from academia (research institutions, research projects), collection data centres (incl. natural history museums), government agencies (nature conservation authorities, national parks and others), expert organisations and citizen science initiatives. Selection criteria were addressing the representability for (1) a certain taxonomic group, (2) a biodiversity tool or technology, (3) a biodiversity database and analysis solution, and (4) the potential for transfer or general applicability to other NFDI4Biodiversity and NFDI activities. Other criteria were related to staffing, such as the availability of qualified, motivated and responsive contact persons with dedicated time allocation for NFDI4Biodiversity. However, this was the starting point and we added more use cases during the course of the project, following experience-driven processes and elaborating criteria (see Box 1 below). An important aspect of the selection process was the anticipated added value for the use case and also for NFDI4Biodiversity: the more it promised to be an exemplary solution, e.g. as a blueprint for workflows in other organisations, the better. This approach increases the likelihood that future use cases will benefit from the developments. The main benefits of the NFDI4Biodiversity activities in the first funding phase were mapped to the needs of four different fictitious but life-like people whose interests and needs cover the consortium's target groups, the so called personas. We chose a nature lover and

conservationist, a post-doc, an institute director and a data manager (<https://www.nfdi4biodiversity.org/en/personas>) and tried to evaluate the benefits of NFDI4Biodiversity through their eyes.

Onboarding Process

Stakeholders interested in becoming an NFDI4Biodiversity use case at a later stage must meet the criteria of the use case policy. New use case stakeholders go through an onboarding process with clearly defined onboarding criteria and process steps (Box 1, Figure 1, supplement Table 1). These are organised into categories, products, portfolios, stakeholders and demands. Use case products can be tangible products that achieve significant impact by supporting NFDI4Biodiversity (e.g. the development of a cloud-based metabarcoding pipeline), fit into the overall network architecture based on data and services, are a useful extension and addition to the use case portfolio (e.g., in terms of taxonomic or geographic coverage) or cover a specific impact in the respective community and user group. Predefined feasibility structures relate to the need for financial and human resources and are structured according to strategic importance, effort, staff capacity and timeframe, and attempt to strike a balance between different user groups. Further criteria relate to the data use and service agreement, the availability of use case partner staff, the availability of NFDI4Biodiversity resources and willingness to comply with the participation rules. Last but not least is a use case profile page on the website, completion of a tangible product, and sustainability of data and services. Benefits include assistance with tools and IT developments, provision of project funds for targeted activities to achieve the NFDI4Biodiversity targets (Flex Fund), and invitations to partner meetings, conferences, and expert workshops.

Figure 1: The use case integration process in NFDI4Biodiversity.

Box 1: Process and criteria for onboarding of new use cases in NFDI4Biodiversity

1. Submission of request via ticket system (documentation)
2. Categorisation
 - a. Service Provider
 - b. Data Provider
 - c. Data Centre
3. Criteria for admission
 - a. Use case outcome
 - i. Concrete product with significant impact through NFDI4Biodiversity support (define scope with project plan)
 - ii. Fit into NFDI4Biodiversity overall concept and architecture: Backend of services as well as delivered data should be FAIR to ensure re-usability.
 - iii. Meaningful extension or addition to the use case portfolio: Representation of the different groups, importance of the respective partners, ratio of effort to result
 - iv. Which user groups are served? Impact in relation to workload: politically-strategically important users, importance of the user group, orientation, gap filling / synergies?
 - b. Feasibility and effort
 - i. Demand for financial and human resources (can use case do most of the work? How much NFDI4Biodiversity capacity is needed and available?)
 - ii. "low vs. high hanging fruits"
 - c. Strategic importance (e.g. representativeness of communities, value of services)
 - d. Timeline: completion feasible by 2025 (tuning with involved TAs)
 - e. Commitment
 - i. Data use and service agreement: Operation, service or data availability; licensing model, right of use, international standards, if applicable.
 - ii. Use case partner: use of own resources, clear definition of objectives & project plan, adherence to schedule
 - iii. NFDI4Bio staff: provision of promised resources, adherence to schedule, responsible persons (project plan)
 - iv. After completion, use cases become partners
4. Estimation of effort (time, costs, personnel, expert communication, priority and necessity) by Use Case Manager, Data and Software Solutions team, Task Area leads
5. Coordination of resource availability
6. Recommendation for admission or rejection by TA1
7. Decision on inclusion by Steering Committee
8. Create use case profile
9. Basic information (description, resources)
10. Assign Use Case Manager
11. Create project plan (concrete products/deliverables, schedule, responsibilities)
12. Start: Use cases can begin when others are completed or staff availability for support and processing is ensured
13. Finalisation
 - a. Present use case in a structured profile page on the website
 - b. Define and finalise concrete product
 - c. Add new services to service portfolio
 - d. Publish data and other results
 - e. Disseminate results through the NFDI4Biodiversity outreach channels

Use Cases – Project Planning

Once a use case is accepted, it is assigned a so-called use case manager from the consortium. Use case managers act as the primary contact and advisor for the respective use case, helping to navigate the project's governance and documentation requirements. The use case manager is in charge of conducting status interviews (see supplement Table 1) using a structured questionnaire. In order to understand the individual requirements, information is gathered on the status, needs, timelines, and resources required for each use case. We were faced with different developmental stages of data management infrastructures and various degrees of dependency on infrastructure components available or planned in NFDI4Biodiversity, such as cloud storage or ontology services. The biodiversity data had different levels of maturity for networking, we met concerns about legal aspects in data sharing as well as a plethora of different tools currently used and needed to improve the data availability according to FAIR principles.

Based on the status interviews, we developed project plans for each of the use cases. These included use case requirements aligned with NFDI4Biodiversity objectives, milestones with defined deliverables, responsibilities for people involved, and timelines to organise interdependent parts of the workflow. These project plans were updated as changes occurred, e.g. in human or financial resources or as the use cases were refocused for various reasons. Individual contacts and communication were maintained throughout the project. Depending on the challenge, other NFDI4Biodiversity task areas and partners were involved, or specific (including virtual) workshops organised to discuss issues of common interest with the partners, like legal aspects. For use cases with similar types of data we sought to standardise existing workflows and pipelines facilitating interoperability from diverse data sources. NFDI4Biodiversity provides support in terms of personnel from a pool of bioinformaticians (Data and Software Solutions team), or financially when external applications were needed to support the use case ideas.

Contributors and Structural Definitions

NFDI4Biodiversity currently includes 26 use case projects (as of 2023, Table 1). Use case partners are generally biodiversity data holders or representatives of user groups that collect, coordinate, analyse, and visualise data. For example, use case partners mainly collect and provide species occurrence data (n = 10; e.g., AraGes, NetPhyD, DNAquaNet) or use these data for derived digital products and services (n = 16; e.g., IPK, IÖR, iDIV, HLNUG). Some use case databases and platforms have online tools for direct capture, storage, or export of datasets, standardised and FAIR, but the monitoring structure varies to some degree between data sources. Some partners are internationally or nationally networked. Sharing data management knowledge from partners with long experience (e.g., museums with databases, international networks, often tenured bioinformaticians familiar with tools, international developments, standards, interoperability, and digital networking strategies) can be a motivator and drive the establishment of database solutions for groups of organisms or communities.

Table 1: Use cases of NFDI4Biodiversity (2023; <https://www.nfdi4biodiversity.org/en/what-we-do/use-cases-uebersicht-1>); Type: RO Research organisations and research projects, PA Public authorities and National Parks, NSA Natural science associations and citizen science projects

Use case	Topic	Type
UC1	eLTER – Network for Long-Term Observations	RO
UC2	Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK)	RO
UC3	AMMOD – A Weather Station for Biodiversity	RO
UC4	German Barcode of Life (GBOL)	RO
UC5	CRITTERBASE – Information system for marine organisms	RO
UC6	Monitor of settlement and open space development (IOER Monitor)	RO
UC7	DNAqua-Net – DNA-based monitoring of freshwater ecosystems	RO
UC8	Naturgucker.de – Information portal for nature observation	NSA
UC9	Insects Saxony – Current and historical insect data	NSA
UC10	Thünen-Institut – Agricultural Atlas	RO
UC11	Saxony-Anhalt State Office for Environmental Protection (LAU)	PA
UC12	Bavarian Forest National Park	PA
UC13	Hessian State Agency for Nature Conservation, Environment and Geology (HLNUG)	PA
UC14	AlgaTerra – Information system for microalgae	RO
UC15	Society of German-speaking Odonatologists e.V. – Dragonfly species in Germany	NSA
UC16	Arachnological Society e.V. – Atlas of Arachnids of Europe	NSA
UC17	Phytodiversity Network Germany e.V. – Deutschlandflora	NSA
UC18	Society for Ichthyology e.V. – Atlas of fish species	NSA
UC19	Leibniz Institute for Regional Geography (IfL) – Spatial Visualisation	RO
UC20	Hunsrück-Hochwald National Park	PA
UC21	Saxon State Office for the Environment, Agriculture and Geology	PA

UC22	German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) – PlantHub	RO
UC23	LAND - Living Atlas of Nature in Germany	NSO/PA
UC24	State Archives of Bavaria	PA
UC25	Umbrella Association of German Avifaunists e.V. – Monitoring data of birds in Germany	NSA
UC26	IGB Berlin - R-package hydrographr	RO

The use cases were initially categorised into four broad typologies based on the type of organisation of the leading partners (academia, data collection centres, governmental agencies, NGOs, Fig. 2). In practice, however, we realised that the goals and approaches of the use case projects did not cluster according to this initial typology. In fact, many use cases are already partly connected through collaborations in existing network structures like GBIF and eLTER or in long-term partnerships, e.g. between associations and natural history collections. In the use case projects, additional partnerships are formed, as in the case of the Bavarian National Park, which is a member of LTER-D and has recently joined the BExIS user community, a tool developed for the Biodiversity Exploratories programme in Germany (see Box 2). In this way, previously disconnected infrastructure projects come together and common practices are disseminated (Fig. 2).

NFDI4Biodiversity thus functions as a distributed resource provider and expert network. Data providers can collaborate with scientific IT centres and developers to implement data management solutions and/or mobilise data for scientific use. Through these collaborations, NFDI4Biodiversity aims to create mutual benefit between partners and add value to the community. In doing so, the adoption of accepted tools and workflows in the domain is encouraged but does not render original or local data infrastructures obsolete. Instead, collaboration serves to find the best solution, the highest level of trust, quality standards, and requirements for each specific domain and community need.

Figure 2: Initially categorised use cases attributed to certain organisation types (academia, collection data centres (e.g. at natural history museums), governmental agencies (e.g. nature conservation authorities, national parks) or associations and citizen science initiatives turned out to be closely affiliated with others. Under the umbrella of NFDI4Biodiversity, other partnerships have emerged and previously unconnected infrastructure projects have been able to network.

User Needs Assessment and Identification of Task Similarities for Mutual Benefits

By conducting interviews, two workshops, multiple online conferences of different consortia, expertise and goals, and one community meeting we first assessed the user needs, and jointly developed strategies and work programmes. For example, data mobilisation, harmonisation and workflow development are challenges that unite seemingly unrelated use case projects across typologies. In the following we discuss how use cases from different types of institutions with different taxonomic scopes, methodologies, biodiversity data types, databases and data platforms benefit from each other.

A collaborative goal for four use cases (AMMOD, GBOL, DNAquanet, AlgaTerra) is the development of a cloud-based analysis pipeline for metabarcoding purposes for different data and reference libraries, storage and publication, visualisation, and review capabilities. This work includes collaboration with ENA (as central repository for the sequence data) and service centres from the German bioinformatics network de.NBI, which are also partners in NFDI4Biodiversity. A common goal of three state agencies (Hesse, Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt) is to link their data in their respective biodiversity information systems (MultiBaseCS). Although all three federal authorities use the same database systems to register species, there are different descriptions of how to collect the data. For example, there is no consensus on whether amphibian juveniles should be reported as clutches or as estimated numbers of juveniles. Each federal authority pre-defined its own set of standards, some of which focus on certain aspects of data collecting. The usual strategy so far has been to agree on a minimum amount of information that the data must contain in order to be useful for national queries. The parameters collected must now be coordinated between the three use cases and integrated into the respective systems (MultibaseCS), so that the data provided are accompanied by more information and an accurate metadata description.

Table 2: Identification of solutions for use cases with mutual benefits. Organisation type: RO Research organisations and research projects, PA Public authorities and National Parks, NSA Natural science associations and citizen science projects

Use Case (UC)	Organisation type	Common Aim	Example problem	Example solution
UC11 - LAU Saxony Anhalt	PA	Exchange of biodiversity relevant information using own System (MultibaseCS)	The state offices record data on the same species differently	Workshops with participants to agree on minimum requirements for the data
UC13 - HLNUG Hessia				
UC21 - LfULG Saxony				
UC15 - GdO	NSA	Linking of the data with each other	Visualising appealing tool for basic data demonstration and analysis	Combined GdO data of one state with Germany-wide Fish data and Land use data in a demonstrator
UC18 - GfI				
UC6 - IÖR	RO			
UC24 - GDA	PA	Data enrichment for more extensive use in research	Data in existing system must be adaptable and extractable	Adding standardised metadata (ABCD)
UC25 - DDA	NSA			
UC10 - Thünen	RO	Improvement of data accessibility and analysis	Making existing data or their analysis easily accessible by means of software developments	Development of an API interface and an R package
UC26 - IGB				
UC2 - IPK	RO	Mobilisation of data	Specific amount of data from existing repositories	Mobilisation of data and potential to add these data into the RDC

UC12 - NP Bayerischer Wald	PA	Improve multi-taxon data management	Data from completed and future projects need to be annotated and managed.	Deployment of a BEXIS2 (data management software) instance and entry of the data there
UC3 - AMMOD	RO	Standardised analysis / storage / publication of metabarcoding data	Different analysis pipelines are used with varying degrees of computing power	Establishment of agreed upon pipelines on the de.NBI computing platform

In addition to pure data mobilisation, several use cases serve to augment existing data with standardised metadata. The standards include biodiversity-relevant data standards like ABCD, endorsed by GBIF, and general standards like bioschemas.org, based on schema.org and are meant to increase data findability via search engines. The need for sharing primary biodiversity data - documentations of biodiversity occurrences through human or automated machine observations, preserved specimens from natural history collections or living organisms in zoos and botanical gardens – has led to the establishment of community standards like DarwinCore (<https://dwc.tdwg.org>) and ABCD (Access to Biological Collections, <https://abcd.tdwg.org>), which are widely used and became relevant for NFDI4Biodiversity use cases (see Box 2).

First Results (in-short)

We have found a great need for legal knowledge about licensing, data ownership and sharing, especially by citizen scientists, or among experts but also in governmental agencies and authorities when the data have been generated in a proprietary way. Especially the transfer of not self-created data into databases is a problem for many downstream users in terms of data protection. Two workshops on legal aspects were conducted and training material has been developed as a result.

In addition, stakeholders benefit from training, tutorials, or best practices. These not only highlight the advantages of a data sharing policy and data annotation plans, but also lead to improved networking among participants and a greater understanding of the significance of data quality as well as existing variations / biases. Understanding the provenance of data used for biodiversity monitoring is crucial in general to guarantee effective integration of data from many sources, including legal considerations for the use of highly protected or sensitive data.

Although the networking of biodiversity data and infrastructures is still at a very early stage and stakeholders are busy setting up communication, management and networking strategies, substantive results have already been achieved that would not have taken place without NFDI4Biodiversity funding and which can serve as a role model for further use cases:

- UC6 and UC15: In a joint effort, data from participants in use case 6 (Land use, land cover) and use case 15 (occurrence data from the German Dragonfly Society) were combined with other environmental data sets in the cloud-enabled geovisualization tool Geo Engine (<https://www.geoengine.de>), to demonstrate potential portal components for partner organisations.
- UC 18: In an ad-hoc project, NFDI4Biodiversity staff and partners contributed to mobilise data on freshwater fish occurrences in the course of the new German Red List for Freshwater fish. The resulting public data set in GBIF (Manthey et al. 2023) was “a first” for the Red List expert group and is used as a best practice story for similar Red List exercises.
- UC26: In a joint use case project with NFDI4Earth, the Waterlink R package was curated and published as a new service for the aquatic biodiversity research community (Üblacker et al. 2023).
- UC12: To enable FAIR data management practices in the Bavarian Forest National Park, a partnership was established with the University of Jena and the Bavarian State Archives General Directorate (GDA). The data of the National Park can now be managed in the information system BEXIS2, developed and hosted by the University Jena for the Biodiversity Exploratories Data Center and others, with new workflows ensuring the required long-term archiving in the Bavarian State Archives (see BOX 2).
- UC24: GDA and Leibniz Institute for Ecological Urban and Regional development (IÖR) established a workflow for the automated extraction of metadata from analog map series, e.g. swamp maps, were generated and linked to the historical data. We are sure that these data will also be of interest for other organism group specific databases.
- UC5: In a joint use case of the Helmholtz Institute for Marine Sciences and the Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, the CRITTERBASE Marine Organisms Data Warehouse (Teschke et al. 2022) was matured and launched as a new data product and service for the marine organisms research community.
- UC22: In a use case of the German Centre for Biodiversity Research iDiv , the development of the PlantHub database is connected to the standards and tool development in NFDI4Biodiversity. A tentative data analysis using data mobilised in PlantHub and cross-linked with publicly available data from iNaturalist yielded surprising results and was published in Nature Ecology & Evolution (Wolf et al. 2022).

Box 2: Some detailed examples of use case activities in NFDI4Biodiversity

Lebendiger Atlas - Natur Deutschland (LAND)

One of our use case products is the "Lebendiger Atlas - Natur Deutschland (LAND)", a national biodiversity portal that provides species occurrence data in Germany to researchers, conservation authorities and the general public. For the development of this portal, we joined forces with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the national node GBIF.de, creating the LAND-portal as a GBIF hosted portal (<https://land.gbif.de/>). The portal integrates species occurrence data from different sources, including monitoring schemes, citizen science, natural history societies, museums and universities. To start with, we mostly stocked the portal with existing datasets from GBIF, including large citizen science datasets such as iNaturalist, observation.org and Naturgucker. A prerequisite for GBIF data is the use of the community standard ABCD which is an important component towards FAIR data. Software implementations exist that allow institutions to share their data like GBIF's Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT, <https://www.gbif.org/ipt>) and BioCASE (Biological Collections Access Service, <https://www.biocase.org>). The German GBIF nodes (<http://www.gbif.de>), all of which are engaged in NFDI4Biodiversity, support use case partners with the implementation of these tools. Now we focus on mobilising new datasets from the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium and beyond. This is supported by e.g. data export in ABCD standard which is recently implemented in the information system BEXIS2 (see below) used by several NFDI4Biodiversity partners. We suggest data delivery of occurrence data in ABCD standard to GBIF as a general pathway to visualise organismal occurrences in Germany in the LAND portal. In this way, the effect of publishing data to GBIF becomes immediately visible for stakeholders.

In March 2023, we held a community workshop with approx. 50 stakeholders from different institutions, launching the portal and inviting feedback and new data contributions. With the LAND portal we do not only establish a one-stop shop for curated biodiversity data in Germany, by mobilising new data sets to GBIF we also make more German biodiversity data openly available to the international research community.

<https://nfdi4biodiversity.org/en/what-we-do/use-case-living-atlas>

Nationalpark Bayerischer Wald

The focus of the Bavarian Forest National Park use case is on "multi-taxon" data – data that encompass not only one but multiple species occurring in a specific area. Data collection in the National Park is carried out using insect traps and cameras. Additionally, environmental factors such as microclimate and forest structure are recorded. NFDI4Biodiversity assists the national park in data management by providing an instance of the information system BEXIS2 developed and hosted by the University Jena, which were established for the Biodiversity Exploratories (Fischer et al. 2010), funded by the German Science Foundation (DFG).

Within the scope of this use case, data storage solutions are being tested that can also benefit other national park administrations. This allows valuable long-term data to be accessible to other interested parties, such as researchers. By providing a BEXIS2 instance through NFDI4Biodiversity and successfully mobilising data of the National Park's BioKlim project, a key objective of the use case has already been achieved. The National Park is also a member of the LTER-D network, through which data from long-term observations are intended to be exchanged with the European research infrastructure eLTER RI via the NFDI4Biodiversity use case eLTER developing respective workflows.

<https://nfdi4biodiversity.org/en/what-we-do/use-case-np-bayerischer-wald>

Integrating a State Archive in data mobilisation

The General Directorate of the State Archives of Bavaria (GDA) is a governmental agency of the Free State of Bavaria. The State Archives have the task of recording, taking over, permanently preserving and securing, indexing, making usable, and evaluating the archival records that have accrued at authorities, courts, and other public offices of the Free State of Bavaria and its predecessors since the advent of written form in administration. Their mandates involve making archive records available for research. The archive material ranges from analogue records such as deeds, files, maps, and audiovisual media to data generated entirely digitally by a wide range of data producers from Bavarian state agencies. Within NFDI4Biodiversity, data on species occurrences has been enriched with structured metadata using the ABCD data standard to increase interoperability. In addition to historical records of flora and wildlife, historical land use data were identified as relevant for the biodiversity community. In collaboration with the Leibniz Institute for Ecological Urban and Regional development (IÖR), old moorland maps were scanned and enhanced with metadata using software created by the IÖR. In collaboration with the Bavarian State Natural Sciences Collections, implementation of the SIARD standard for archiving relational databases has been tested, reacting to user needs identified in the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium. This work is also the basis for developing a long-term archiving concept for data from the BioKlim project of the Bavarian Forest National Park.

<https://nfdi4biodiversity.org/en/what-we-do/use-case-bavaria-state-archives>

Lessons Learned

The first phase has been characterised by dealing with the 26 use cases by extensive networking efforts during onboarding, concrete conception of the use cases, and the aspiration to build trust among all participating partners. During this phase, there were use case partners who demonstrated significant commitment and, right from the beginning, gave input with their expertise and existing infrastructure. Some use cases were more reserved or less well-equipped initially, but their specific development has progressed quite well in the course of the project, yielding remarkable results. Unfortunately, there were also use cases that likely had higher expectations from their involvement in NFDI4Biodiversity, and some of them may have been disappointed thus far. This was mainly caused by interdependencies with the development of RDC which turned out to take more time than expected.

Stakeholder Engagement

The advantages of establishing national data networks, as exemplified by NFDI4Biodiversity, lie in the collaborative creation of shared expertise (bioinformaticians, informaticians, taxonomists, ecologists and others), shared technique (e.g. RDC and tools), shared data and shared data products (e.g. LAND), benefiting the biodiversity community and beyond. Long-term management, as envisioned by NFDI4Biodiversity requires computer literacy, standardisation and documentation skills, and the ability to oversee the maintenance and upkeep of data management systems. In this way, NFDI4Biodiversity fosters **stakeholder integration, self-organisation, and knowledge transfer**. As a result, **successful examples and role models are essential for demonstrating the benefits of increased visibility and interoperability**. In addition to these demonstrations, qualified employees provide vital and invaluable assistance and additional education on all aspects of the data lifecycle.

Working in transdisciplinary teams with colleagues from various backgrounds made it especially important to develop a common understanding of the goals, roles, and working modes adopted in the various use cases. Communication between users and programmers can be difficult due to differences in understanding and terminology, time availability, and constraints. The **use case managers** therefore have an important role as mediators and contact persons between the different experts, for project planning, communication and management, as well as visibility and representation for NFDI4Biodiversity and the German biodiversity data community.

Thanks to good project management, very **efficient and clear governance structures** have been established in NFDI4Biodiversity. However, continuous adherence to these structures is not always a given and represents a trade-off between forward-thinking commitment and administrative time. We have learned that personal commitment to compliance with governance structures is important, and must be continuously promoted and communicated.

Commitment of individuals at partner organisations is needed, sometimes motivated by funding, sometimes intrinsic motivation is available (many citizen scientists). Organisations facing **staffing bottlenecks** and who have to focus on competing local tasks shy away from the additional effort of active and continuous participation in NFDI4Biodiversity use cases. It has become apparent that some use case partners do not have the time, staff, or simply the determination to move forward with their initial projects. This has created quite a dilemma for the consortium: on the one hand, we obviously wanted to include and welcome as many strategic partners as possible into our community. On the other hand, the success of the project depends on the strong commitment and determination of the partners. Thus, we currently have partner institutions, acting in the manner of passive observers rather than actively driving agents of their respective use cases.

In terms of financial support, the **Flexfunds pool** created in 2022 was an excellent mechanism to spark engagement and drive activity. It allowed our partners to apply for funds for very clearly defined smaller projects or to solve specific problems in networking, tool development, analysis or training processes in their own time. Although the possible preference for partners who are already well or sufficiently staffed and funded should be noted here, the deliberate promotion of smaller, clearly defined projects can be very productive.

For continuous engagement, **credibility** is key; and in terms of infrastructure, only continuity leads to credibility. If the IT infrastructure offered to the community is based on project funding, this can be conducive to innovation and progress in terms of tools and technology, but ultimately users will require dependable infrastructures and stick to their own, easier to control systems if community solutions appear unstable or at risk.

In order to motivate and engage new disciplines and communities in NFDI4Biodiversity in the future, we therefore recommend the establishment of **interest groups** that bring together people with diverse viewpoints and expertise to help the network address critical issues and problems related to biodiversity data. These recommendations should result in a written report that can be implemented as needed. For example: the success of data integration hinges on a **diverse understanding of data** (e.g. tadpoles are documented in some databases individually, in others only mature frogs are listed, which needs expert knowledge for networking databases), the usage of universally accepted international standards, and the utilisation of interoperable and/or specialised databases (e.g., DNA barcoding repositories are currently emerging, while biodiversity data is already being gathered). It requires the dedicated efforts of knowledgeable professionals who possess a deep understanding of their data, the databases they work with, and the respective communities they serve. Involving experts is essential, but their availability is often limited due to the limited number of highly qualified and motivated experts. Stakeholders with a practical way of working and a clear mission in terms of their output could reduce staff bottlenecks for others, allowing experts to focus their time availability.

Communication

We learned that collaborating remotely with colleagues distributed in approx. 50 partner organisations all over Germany has its own challenges. After the COVID pandemic, many colleagues have shown a certain fatigue with online meetings. For trust building we discovered the importance of regular in-person or online meetings and the regular participation in community-specific conferences, meetings and workshops, and the publication of articles in the respective community-specific journals. Integrating stakeholders through a network requires the establishment and maintenance of the network, not only through ongoing personal outreach but also with clear governance structures, distribution of tasks, knowledge sharing, priorities, and bioinformatics developments. At the heart of good governance is genuine partner engagement, mutual trust and satisfaction to ensure the network is fit for purpose and on target. To this end, we conduct

quarterly online partner meetings and 1-2 annual on-site community workshops. To foster the community spirit, we thus cannot overemphasise the **importance of in-person meetings**. The NFDI4Biodiversity All Hands Conferences as well as various smaller project meetings have worked wonders in raising the spirits of our staff and bringing derailed projects back on track. The main challenge is to ensure the continuous flow of resources necessary for the operation, quality, and acceptance of NFDI4Biodiversity.

For communication optimization, a **collaborative wiki platform** and a ticket system implemented by the central project coordination for project management and coordination has on the one hand been extremely helpful to oversee and consolidate the different activities in the consortium. Protocols, products and findings are first made available here and after an internal review process published with open access. All these measures are aimed at continuously building trust between the actors involved in order to promote cooperation and ensure the quality and continuity of the joint networking tasks. On the other hand, it has also burdened our partners with an increasing bureaucratic and administrative load that did not always increase the willingness to collaborate. This has been especially problematic for partners of understaffed data infrastructures, or those with many volunteers or infrequent users.

Aims and Goals

Throughout the various use cases, it has been an ongoing process in which the different partners have repeatedly **reviewed and revised the goals and working plans** of the use case projects. Clear but adaptive working plans have been key to successful collaboration, but have not always been possible. We have learned that goals, roles, contacts, and ways of working in the various use cases sometimes change over the course of a five-year-project like ours. Often, details and stumbling blocks are only recognized in the course of a work process. As a result, some flexibility in project planning and execution is required, and even established goals and timelines shift due to resource constraints. This underscores the importance of content, notes, and paraphrases on the status of introductory interviews where we strongly recommend the use of pre-formulated interview guides (see supplements S1). Defining the same or having an open dialogue with audio recordings of the conversations and subsequent transcriptions for qualitative textual analysis would potentially strengthen clearer agreements earlier in the use case as contacts or goals change. However, changes in goals cannot be avoided, and in this context, some processes are quite simple and straightforward and can be resolved more quickly than initially anticipated, while other processes take significantly more time and are delayed. It is important to be cautious, as data mobilization can be a never-ending process, but one that requires clear, timely goals and intermediate deliverables. Use case projects should therefore tend to be kept small, limited in time, and have a clear goal in terms of deliverables. Otherwise, coordinating and managing more than two dozen use cases becomes unmanageable.

Motivation and Technical Developments

Benefits and incentives to participate in NFDI4Biodiversity for many are the **provision of data and technical infrastructure at different levels of the Research Data Commons architecture**. Examples include the operation of data management systems in the cloud, data transformations with semantic tools, the use of temporary object storage, or the operation of own applications on servers in the NFDI Multi-Cloud. Initially, NFDI4Biodiversity planned to provide use cases early on with services and workflows that are not feasible or cannot be implemented efficiently with the partner institutions' in-house resources and only become economical through cooperative operation. These new ideas for joint biodiversity data management and analysis do motivate the community to engage with the NFDI. However, given the actual time and effort required for pilot users of such a rather complex self-service platform, careful expectation management is needed. The presentation of NFDI4biodiversity infrastructure offerings available at the time of notification may be an issue. It is likely that both over-promotion of offerings that are not yet available and a lack of promotion may lead to disappointment among use case partners. Here, the importance of use case managers in providing clear communication and acting as points of contact when problems arise should be highlighted. However, our work confirmed real user needs for centralized cloud services (duplicate discovery, versioning, synonymy servers, and synchronisation of tools and services).

In terms of tool usage, however, there may also be restrictions that result from existing limitations in the use of existing technology/software. Due to their respective IT policies or other formal regulations, some organisations, such as government agencies, are not free to choose which software and services can be used. This starts with big tech companies' services which tend to be in conflict with established European data protection and data privacy regulations. The use of free software without professional long-term support is not acceptable for some institutions. Integrating use case data with data that already exists at other institutions often requires agreement on formats, data schemas, and metadata before technical integration can be implemented. The goal of this integration is to link data from different sources to create value for the use case and the community. Appropriate processes are needed to show whether and what data is mobilised and made available, **because not every data holder will make all data FAIR**, and there is always potential for optimisation. Statistical methods can facilitate the integration and qualitative assessment of data from multiple sources to determine biodiversity status and change and identify sampling errors and biases within observation datasets (Isaac et al. 2020, Turner et al. 2022). With the abundance of data available, statistical analysis and data visualisation are becoming increasingly relevant. **Data reuse through integration, visualisations**, or other overview tools are extremely useful for large-scale biodiversity monitoring (Turner 2022).

The **tool implementation** is important, e.g. API programming (data mobilisation), provision of software tools (e.g., the Bexis 2 information system), RDC infrastructure, data visualisation tools, tools for data analysis, and winter schools. When new services result from use cases, it is important that they are applicable

and well documented. However, sometimes, expectations, e.g., of specific tool usage are caught up in cloud computing advancements and turn out to be null and void. The publication of tools can lead to their usage by previously unanticipated communities, e.g. in the field of water analysis (IGB Berlin Hydrographr, Metabarcoding). However, the tools are only useful with mobilised data. Close collaboration and continuous feedback with users is needed to ensure that the tools developed also meet user needs. In the future, a presentation of the tools developed within NFDI4Biodiversity is needed to add value for further applications or to extend existing tools for further needs.

Training in the use of cloud services and data analysis tools with large computing power or complex programs and analyses is of great interest to the biodiversity community. The one-week Winter School organised in collaboration with GfÖ was a great success. Videos and presentations have been made available in the NFDI4Biodiversity YouTube channel and Zenodo community, and the concept was published as a blueprint for future Winter Schools (Röder et al 2023). There is still an urgent need for a cultural change as sharing data is not a given among data holding communities and individuals. The topic has not yet found its way into research groups, undergraduate and graduate curricula. Cultural change requires education, training, incentives and ergonomic data management processes to become the standard for delivering FAIR data. There is a need for university showcase models that can serve as examples for others (e.g., installation and training for long-term use of BEXIS systems in universities). Broad collaboration, communication, development of training materials, provision of benefits, top down incentives and bottom-up motivation etc. is needed here. This cannot be handled by a national biodiversity data infrastructure alone, but requires direct contact with the grassroots, such as university IT support centres or regional initiatives (e.g. in collaboration with HeFDI in Hesse) as well as the evolving data competence centres in Germany. **Digital training and educational materials for self-study units are of high value** and should be promoted further.

The legally correct handling of data is still a relatively unknown and not fully solved issue in the biodiversity context. Some project partners offered legal training, but it did not necessarily reach the grassroots of data collectors, especially from governmental monitoring programs, who might be rather skeptical about data sharing. To address this challenge, low-threshold advice to stakeholders on such legal/data licensing issues is needed. For example, a legal help-desk for use case projects would be helpful, perhaps in collaboration with other NFDI consortia.

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Supplement

Questionnaire for Use Case status interviews

(questions in bold)

Topic area: Goals and motivation

What are your goals for your organisation in general? What is important and profitable to you?

Goals could be:

- *Networking people with the same interests*
- *Creating a data base for natural history interests/ for official reporting requirements/ for science and research /*
- *nature conservation*

What is the biggest motivation for your organisation to participate in the NFDI4BioDiversity project?

Motivations could be:

- *Harmonize reference lists*
- *Adapt and improve workflows*
- *Participate in the NFDI4BioDiversity community*

Topic area: Initial situation; data, databases, or data structures.

What is the baseline situation in your organization?

Topic area: goals for the data, databases, or data structures.

The overarching goal is the RDC with the cloud infrastructure. The NFDI RDC provide the space for a variety of intermediary services to operate between the needs of data demanders and producers. These services are organized in different "layers" that provide end users with easy access to relevant data from various sources and associated services.

Respective objectives from the NFDI4Biodiversity proposal:

- (1) Compiling information on small-scale national land use/cover databases
- (2) Contributions to the standardization of land use classifications and nomenclatures
- (3) Development of advanced indicators (including soil types, fertility, sealed land surface, fragmentation, urban sprawl); dissemination of information and training on research data on land use/cover.

Who are the contacts in your organisation for the areas listed below?

How much time would you have for collaboration, or when is the best time to contact them?

Contact person (name / email / phone; when to contact?) and expertise:

- IT / Software
- Biological expertise
- Data / data management

For what other tasks, if any, technical support is needed (in NFDI4Biodiversity or in general)?

Important: This may not be solved within this project (or with resources from this project).

Topic area: Timing and organization

According to the financial plan of the NFDI4BioDiversity project, the following resources are foreseen for your organization (in addition, there are available resources in terms of technical expertise and support from other partners in the NFDI4BioDiversity consortium):

Number of person months, spread over project runtime.

The IT development team is located at the Gesellschaft für Biologische Daten e.V. (Society for Biological Data). Person-months can be called upon to customize IT solutions, for your needs or to perform data migrations.

Important: The NFDI4BioDiversity project team will conduct initial interviews with all partner organizations in March and April. Based on the information from these conversations, the roadmap for implementing the various projects will be completed.

Which of the needs identified above do you see as most urgent?

What should we start with?

What time horizons are realistic/desirable for you?

Important: Whether these "wishes" are feasible will only become clear once all status discussions have been concluded and our internal planning has been completed.

Are there specific time horizons that need to be considered?

Topic area: Pitfalls and challenges

What potential challenges, hurdles, or pitfalls do you see that could affect effective and focused collaboration within the NFDI4BioDiversity program?

What would need to happen for NFDI4BioDiversity to be attractive to the broader biodiversity community or for potential barriers to be removed?